

MI: A Sophisticated Hardware-Simulator for Student Education

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Abstract

MI is a German acronym and stands for *Maschine für die Informatik-Ausbildung*. It has been used since 1985 at the Technische Universität München, and since 1987 at a variety of other German universities in order to train a few thousand students in machine-oriented programming and basics of operating systems and compiler construction. Today, MI supports a graphical interface and can be used as a testbed for the efficient programming of a simulated 32-bit-4-processor-hardware.

In this paper we show how MI has been used at the Technische Universität München for undergraduate education in machine-oriented programming. First, we give an overview of the simulator architecture. Second, we demonstrate the simulator by discussing the creation of a simple assembler program, and finally, we briefly describe the graphical user interface of MI.

MI has been ported to multi-vendor hardware running DOS or UNIXes and is available on request.

1. INTRODUCTION

MI can be used as a testbed for efficient programming of a simulated 32-bit-4-processor-hardware without being involved with a real hardware. However, all aspects of “dirty” programming on a bare machine are covered, such as multi-level interrupt handling, memory-mapped IO for peripheral devices, two working modes (user mode and kernel mode), two modes of addressing (absolute and virtual). In addition to a machine-oriented programming language, fully interactive debugging facilities are provided.

Due to different modes and an easy to use graphical debugging system, a step by step approach can be used

- to learn things like addressing and manipulation of data in main memory, or
- to write a disk driver for simulated disks, or
- to implement the addressing and manipulation of data via secondary storage using page table entries that can be as complicated as in a real virtual memory system, or
- to understand how data are transferred between modules, or
- to see how data access by different processors can be synchronized.

Last but not least, the students can learn to handle interrupts, to change from user mode to system mode via system calls, or to invoke instruction processor-traps at other processors and handle them. Obviously, in this context, there is a variety of different applications that can be used for student education. In Munich we use mainly two: (a) applications to build a basic operating system on top of MI using its assembler programming, and (b) basic compiler applications to create code for MI that is tested and run on MI.

The non-graphical version of MI is easily portable. It is written in PASCAL and C, respectively, and runs as a simple user application on top of various operating systems. The graphical version, on the other hand, requires an installation of InterViews 3.x.

This paper cannot cover all aspects of MI. It should simply give an idea what MI does. For more details refer to [3] or contact the author. Section 2 gives an overview of the simulator architecture. Section 3 demonstrates the simulator by discussing the creation of a small assembler program, and Section 4 describes the graphical user interface and its debugging facilities.

2. ARCHITECTURE

MI consists of the following basic components: 4 simulated instruction processors (IP_1, \dots, IP_4), one simulated IO-processor (IOP_1) that controls 2 simulated disk drives, one simulated IO-processor (IOP_2) that controls 4 simulated duplex-channels, e.g., terminal and printer channels, and simulated main memory. These components are connected through a simulated shared bus system (see Figure 1). The instruction processors as well as the IO-processors operate concurrently.

Figure 1. Architectural components of MI.

Each instruction processor has 16 programmable registers, and a variety of special registers such as the program status word or the initial priority level.

The smallest addressable unit of the main memory is a byte. Objects in main memory, however, can have the following formats: **B** (byte, char) 8 bit, **H** (half-word) 16 bit, **W** (word) 32 bit, **F** (floating-point) 32 bit, and **D** (double-float) 64 bit. The interpretation of a particular bitstring is instruction-dependent as well as format-dependent, i.e., integer, char, or full IEEE floating-point arithmetic.

Example: (floating-point/double-float¹)

sign: $(-1)^s$, where $s = b_0 \in \{0, 1\}$.

exponent: The floating-point exponent e is a m -bit fraction biased² by 127, i.e., $e = \sum_{i=1}^m b_i \times 2^{m-i}$, where $b_i \in \{0, 1\}$ and $0 \leq e \leq 2^m - 1$.

mantissa: The floating-point mantissa f is a n -bit fraction which, together with an implicit leading 1, yields the significant digit field “1.-”, i.e., $f = \sum_{i=1}^n b_{m+i} \times 2^{-i} = 2^{-n} \times \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} b_{m+n-j} \times 2^j$, where $0 \leq f < 1$.

value: Let e_{max} be $2^m - 1$ and e^* be $2^{m-1} - 1$. Then, we distinguish the following five cases of value v for a floating-point number:

- (1) $0 < e < e_{max}$: $v = (-1)^s \times 2^{e-e^*} \times (1 + f)$ (normalized)
- (2) $e = 0 \wedge f = 0$: $v = (-1)^s \times 0$
- (3) $e = e_{max} \wedge f = 0$: $v = (-1)^s \times \infty$ (overflow)
- (4) $e = e_{max} \wedge f \neq 0$: $v = \text{not-a-number (NaN)}$
- (5) $e = 0 \wedge f \neq 0$: $v = (-1)^s \times 2^{-(e^*-1)} \times f$ (denormalized)

The task of constructing reliable floating-point software is made easy due to the fact that MI is supportive of correct floating-point arithmetic.

3. PROGRAMMING MI

Figure 2 shows the central part of a small MI-program that calculates the n -th fibonacci number.³ For simplicity the program operates in kernel mode with absolute addressing, and is written for a single instruction processor. Due to its highly recursive character, this program is a good example to realize the pulsation of the run-time stack for its various incarnations.

```

fib      : PUSHR                -- procedure fib
          MOVEA 64+!SP,R12
          MOVE  W SP,R13
if       : CMP  W !R12,I 1      -- n<=1?
          JGT   else
then     : MOVE  W I 1,4+!R12    -- result is 1
          JUMP  endif
else     : CLEAR W -!SP         -- space for result1
          SUB  W I 1,!R12,-!SP  -- push current parameter
          CALL fib              -- fib(n-1)
          ADD  W I 4,SP         -- free top stack word
          CLEAR W -!SP         -- space for result2
          SUB  W I 2,!R12,-!SP  -- push current parameter
          CALL fib              -- fib(n-2)
          ADD  W I 4,SP         -- free top stack word
          ADD  W !SP+,!SP+,4+!R12
endif    : ...

```

Figure 2. Fragment of an MI assembler program.

In case the program is syntactically correct, MI’s assembler routine generates the corresponding executable code file, and files containing a listing (Figure 3), cross references, and an

¹ $m = 8$ and $n = 23$ for floating-point, $m = 11$ and $n = 52$ for double-float.

²double-float is biased by 1023.

³the full program can be seen in the TEXT and COMMENT columns, respectively, of Figure 3.

address book (Figure 4). Otherwise all errors are marked and displayed. A special debugging feature allows to jump from error to error for correction. This is convenient if there are only some typing errors in a very large program.

```

LINE LABEL ADDRESS CODE TEXT COMMENT
  1 toy: SEG -- fibonacci numbers
  2 00000000 A0 8F00010000 5E MOVE W I H'10000',SP -- stack initialization
  3 00000007 F1 AF09 JUMP start
  4 -- variables
  5 n: 0000000A 0000000B DD W 11
  6 erg: 0000000E 00000000 DD W 0
  7
  8 start: 00000012 9B 7E CLEAR W -!SP -- space for result
  9 00000014 A0 AFF4 7E MOVE W n,-!SP -- push(n)
 10 00000018 F2 AF09 CALL fib -- fib(n)
 11 0000001B C1 04 5E ADD W I 4,SP -- free top stack word
 12 0000001E A0 8E AFED MOVE W !SP+,erg -- result in erg
 13 00000022 00 HALT -- dynamic end
 14
 15 fib: 00000023 F4 PUSHR -- procedure fib
 16 00000024 AB AE40 5C MOVEA 64+!SP,R12
 17 00000028 A0 5E 5D MOVE W SP,R13
 18 if: 0000002B 94 6C 01 CMP W !R12,I 1 -- n<=1?
 19 0000002E EB AF08 JGT else
 20 then: 00000031 A0 01 AC04 MOVE W I 1,4+!R12 -- result is 1
 21 00000035 F1 AF1E JUMP endif
 22 else: 00000038 9B 7E CLEAR W -!SP -- space for result1
 23 0000003A D0 01 6C 7E SUB W I 1,!R12,-!SP -- push current parameter
 24 0000003E F2 AFE3 CALL fib -- fib(n-1)
 25 00000041 C1 04 5E ADD W I 4,SP -- free top stack word
 26 00000044 9B 7E CLEAR W -!SP -- space for result2
 27 00000046 D0 02 6C 7E SUB W I 2,!R12,-!SP -- push current parameter
 28 0000004A F2 AFD7 CALL fib -- fib(n-2)
 29 0000004D C1 04 5E ADD W I 4,SP -- free top stack word
 30 00000050 C6 8E 8E AC04 ADD W !SP+,!SP+,4+!R12
 31 -- fib(n) = fib(n-1) + fib(n-2)
 32 endif: 00000055 A0 5D 5E MOVE W R13,SP
 33 00000058 F5 POPR
 34 00000059 F3 RET -- end of procedure fib
 35 END -- static end

```

Figure 3. Generated listing of the MI assembler program.

CROSS-REFERENCES:				ADDRESS BOOK:		
LABEL	SEGMENT	LINE	NUMBER	LABEL	SEGMENT	ADDRESS
else	toy	22	19	else	toy	00000038
endif	toy	32	21	endif	toy	00000055
erg	toy	6	12	erg	toy	0000000E
fib	toy	15	28 24 10	fib	toy	00000023
if	toy	18		if	toy	0000002B
n	toy	5	9	n	toy	0000000A
start	toy	8	3	start	toy	00000012
then	toy	20		then	toy	00000031
toy		1		toy		00000000

Figure 4. Generated cross-references and address book of the MI assembler program.

4. GRAPHICAL INTERFACE

As soon as the assembler program has been successfully “compiled”, the corresponding code file (often referred to as load module) may be executed. Thereby the graphical interface together with its debugging facilities provide a wide range of possible traces at runtime.

Figure 5. Graphical interface for a single instruction processor.

The graphical interface for a single instruction processor as shown in Figure 5 contains

- the Listing Window. This browsing window displays the listing of the assembler program and highlights the instruction currently processed.
- the Simulation Controls. Here the students can set basic debugging mechanisms such as continuous refresh, backtrace, stop, go, restart, and quit.
- the CPU-Display. It shows the up-to-date content of the 16 programmable registers.
- the Output Window. This window displays simulator messages, e.g., error messages.
- the Command Line. Here multi-line commands, so-called *bodies*, can be given.
- the Stack Display. This window displays the up-to-date content of the run-time stack either by absolute addresses or by stack-relative addresses.
- the display for Special Registers. This window displays the up-to-date content of the special registers of the instruction processor. Interactively, the initial priority level or the program status word can be manipulated.
- the Memory Map. It shows the current content of a predefined range of main memory addresses. The display mode may be set to ASCII, decimal, floating-point, etc.

The display for special registers as well as the memory map are only visible on request.

4.1. Breakpoints, Single Step Mode and Backtracing

The students can interactively set breakpoints to any relevant instruction by simply clicking the instruction in question within the listing window. Breakpoints can be set, furthermore, to absolute addresses or a range of addresses. But most importantly, it is possible to trace interrupts, external as well as internal interrupts, and to watch for store or fetch accesses to data in main memory, respectively. The default response to an interrupt is to deliver a specified result that is written to the stack, and to offer a trap to user software at the option of the multi-level interrupt handler. All operations are conceptually serial. When an interrupt occurs, it is possible to identify the operation and its operands.

The coding of the interrupt handler should be an essential part of the assembler program that causes the trap. MI provides all mechanisms to develop the interrupt handler. The coding itself, however, is due to the programmer. This kind of coding is typically one of the last steps during an undergraduate course using MI.

During the semantical check of an assembler program, it is often useful to trace the program run step by step, or to backtrace the last instructions when a predefined event has been reached. These features are provided as well.

4.2. Error Level for Peripheral Devices

An interesting application in assembler programming is the development of device drivers, e.g., for disk drives, terminal, or printer. Often, the goal is to design reliable and highly fault-tolerant drivers.

MI provides for setting of different error levels for peripheral devices. The students can simulate a device that is fully reliable, i.e., no errors occur during data transmission, or he/she can choose a device where (in the average) one out of 4096, 1024, 256, 64, or 4 data transmissions prove faulty. This feature can be used, for instance, to develop a bad sector management for the two simulated disk drives, stable storage, or whatsoever.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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